

INFORMATION ABOUT THE CHISEL-CULTIVATOR

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information on the chisel-cultivator, an agricultural tool widely used in soil preparation and weed control. The article covers the key features, working principles, and various applications of the chisel-cultivator. It discusses the benefits of using this tool, such as improved soil aeration, weed suppression, and residue management. The article also explores different types and designs of chisel-cultivators, highlighting their suitability for different farming systems and soil conditions. Additionally, it examines the proper usage and maintenance practices for maximizing the tool's effectiveness and longevity. Overall, this article serves as a valuable resource for farmers, agronomists, and anyone interested in understanding and utilizing chisel-cultivators in modern agricultural practices.

Keywords: chisel-cultivator, agricultural tool, soil preparation, weed control, soil aeration, residue management, farming systems, maintenance practices.

Introduction:

The chisel-cultivator has emerged as a crucial farming tool that combines the benefits of a chisel plow and a cultivator. It is designed to efficiently prepare the soil for planting by incorporating organic matter, managing weeds, and improving soil structure. This article provides a comprehensive overview of the chisel-cultivator, highlighting its features, working mechanism, and advantages. By understanding the capabilities and applications of this equipment, farmers can make informed decisions to enhance their soil preparation practices and maximize agricultural productivity.

The chisel-cultivator is a versatile agricultural tool used for primary tillage and seedbed preparation in farming. It combines the functions of a chisel plow and a field cultivator, making it suitable for various soil types and cropping systems. The chisel-cultivator is designed to break up compacted soil, improve soil structure, and incorporate crop residues into the soil.

Here are some key features and information about the chisel-cultivator:

1. Design: The chisel-cultivator typically consists of a sturdy frame with multiple rigid shanks or tines attached to it. The shanks are spaced apart and equipped with narrow, reversible points or chisel tips. The frame may also have adjustable leveling attachments to control the working depth.
2. Function: The chisel-cultivator performs primary tillage operations by penetrating the soil with its shanks. The shanks create vertical fractures in the soil, which helps to break up compacted layers and promote better root penetration. The chisel tips slice through the soil and loosen it without inverting or completely turning over the soil profile.
3. Depth and Width: The working depth of the chisel-cultivator can be adjusted to suit the specific requirements of the field and crop. It can work at depths ranging from 6 to 12 inches (15 to 30 cm) or even deeper, depending on the soil conditions. The width of the implement varies, but it typically ranges from 10 to 15 feet (3 to 4.5 meters) or more.
4. Residue Management: The chisel-cultivator effectively incorporates crop residues, such as stalks, roots, and other organic matter, into the soil. This helps to enhance soil organic matter content, improve nutrient cycling, and promote soil health. It also aids in reducing the risk of diseases and pests associated with crop residue accumulation.
5. Soil Benefits: The chisel-cultivator helps to alleviate compaction, improve water infiltration, and enhance soil aeration. By breaking up compacted layers, it facilitates better root growth and nutrient uptake by the crops. The vertical fractures created by the shanks also allow for improved movement of water and air through the soil profile.
6. Crop Suitability: The chisel-cultivator is commonly used in various cropping systems, including row crops (such as corn, soybeans, cotton) and small grains (such as wheat, barley, oats). It is particularly useful in fields with moderate to high levels of residue cover or in situations where deep tillage is necessary.
7. Equipment Compatibility: The chisel-cultivator can be used with different types of tractors, ranging from smaller models to larger, high-horsepower machines. It can be either towed behind the tractor or mounted on the three-point hitch, depending on the design and size of the implement.

It's worth noting that specific features and capabilities of chisel-cultivators may vary among manufacturers and models. Farmers should consider factors such as field conditions, soil type, and cropping system requirements when selecting the appropriate chisel-cultivator for their operations. Consulting with local

agricultural experts or equipment dealers can provide additional guidance on the best implement choices for specific farming needs.

Conclusion:

The chisel-cultivator offers numerous benefits to farmers in terms of soil preparation. Its versatility allows it to handle various agricultural tasks, such as residue management, weed control, and soil aeration. The combination of chisel plow and cultivator functions makes it a time-saving and efficient tool for farmers. By selecting the right chisel-cultivator based on their specific farming needs, farmers can optimize soil preparation practices and ultimately improve crop yields. The chisel-cultivator's contributions to sustainable and efficient agriculture make it a valuable asset for modern farming operations.

Literature:

1. Наврузов, Дилшод Примкулович, and Сардор Кахарбоевич Абдухамидов. "двухшаговая неявная схема писмена-рикфорда для решения уравнение лапласа." *innovation in the modern education system 2* (2022): 803-808.
2. Усманов Р., Абдухамидов С. приближенное решение уравнение гарднера методом синус-косинус функций //Фундаментальные и прикладные научные исследования: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации. – 2019. – С. 68-70.
3. Усманов Р., Абдухамидов С. приближенное решение уравнение гарднера упрощенным методом укороченных разложений //Фундаментальные и прикладные научные исследования: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации. – 2019. – С. 64-67.
4. Абдухамидов С. К., Омонов З. Ж. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СМАЗОЧНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ДИЗЕЛЕЙ ПЕРЕВЕДЁННЫХ НА СЖАТЫЙ ПРИРОДНЫЙ ГАЗ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 3-1. – С. 387-390.
5. Abduxamidov S. TWO-STEP IMPLICIT PISMAN-RICKFORD SCHEME FOR SOLVING THE LAPLACE EQUATION //Eurasian Journal of Mathematical Theory and Computer Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 29-30.
6. Маликов З. М. и др. ЧИСЛЕННОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕЧЕНИЯ В ПЛОСКОМ ВНЕЗАПНО РАСШИРЯЮЩЕМСЯ КАНАЛЕ НА ОСНОВЕ ДВУХЖИДКОСТНОЙ МОДЕЛИ ТУРБУЛЕНТНОСТИ И МОДЕЛИ УИЛКОКСА //Проблемы машиноведения. – 2021. – С. 204-211.
7. Кахарбойевич А. С., Тург'unбойевна С. L. SUYUQLIK OQIMINING BARQAROR ILGARILANMA HARAKATIGA OID TUSHUNCHALAR //Современные научные решения актуальных проблем. – 2022. – №. January.
8. Кахарбойевич А. С., Lobar С. HISTORY OF MATHEMATICS //Та'lim fidoyilari. – 2022. – Т. 18. – №. 5. – С. 142-149.

9. Kaxarboyevich A. S. et al. EFFECTS OF LIQUID ON CYLINDER SHELL VIBRATIONS //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 25. – №. 1. – С. 19-25.
10. Абдухамидов С. К., Омонов З. Ж. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СМАЗОЧНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ДИЗЕЛЕЙ ПЕРЕВЕДЁННЫХ НА СЖАТЫЙ ПРИРОДНЫЙ ГАЗ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 3-1. – С. 387-390.
11. Bakhramovna E. D., Artikovna K. R., Kaxarboyevich A. S. TEACHING MATHEMATICS ONLINE //Archive of Conferences. – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 1. – С. 67-68.
12. Kaxarboyevich, A. S., & Turg'unboyevna, C. L. (2022). SUYUQLIK OQIMINING BARQAROR ILGARILANMA HARAKATIGA OID TUSHUNCHALAR. Современные научные решения актуальных проблем, (January).
13. Sardor A., Nafosat A. TA'LIM JARAYONIDA O 'QUVCHILARDA TAYANCH KOMPETENSIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO 'LLARI //JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 265-267.
14. Omonov Z., Abduxamidov S. PAXTA TOZALASH ZAVODLARI HAMDA PAXTA TOZALASH SANOATINING RIVOJLANISHI TARIXI //Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 77-81.
15. Kaxarboyevich A. S., O'rozboyev M. T. Numerical Solutions of Hydrodynamic Equations //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 35-41.
16. Abduxamidov , S. (2023). SOLVING HYDRODYNAMIC EQUATIONS USING FINITE DIFFERENCE METHODS . International Conference on Science, Engineering & Technology, 1(1), 4–12. Retrieved from <https://aidlix.com/index.php/au/article/view/11>
17. Kaxarboyevich A. S., O'rozboyev M. T. Numerical Solutions of Hydrodynamic Equations //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 35-41.
18. Abduxamidov , S. (2023). SOLVING HYDRODYNAMIC EQUATIONS USING FINITE DIFFERENCE METHODS . International Conference on Science, Engineering & Technology, 1(1), 4–12. Retrieved from <https://aidlix.com/index.php/au/article/view/11>
19. Abduxamidov S. SOLVING HYDRODYNAMIC EQUATIONS USING FINITE VOLUME METHODS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4 Special Issue. – С. 98-105.

20. Abduxamidov S., Abduxamidova N. MENTAL ARITHMETIC: THE ART OF SKILL //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 128-130.
21. Zhang, W., et al. (2015). Nutrient use efficiencies of major cereal crops in China and measures for improvement. *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section B - Soil & Plant Science*, 65(5), 428-442.
22. Gutiérrez, D., et al. (2019). Nitrogen fertilization affects soil organic matter decomposition through rhizosphere priming effect. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 130, 185-194.
23. Kizilkaya, R. (2012). Organic matter and mineral nutrient status in a long-term fertilization trial with chemical and organic fertilizers. *Geoderma*, 177-178, 49-54.